

Synthesis, characterization, preliminary molecular docking, pharmacological activity, and ADME studies of some new pyrazoline derivatives as anti-breast cancer agents

Hayder R. Fadhil^{1,2}, Ayad M. R. Raauf³, Monther F. Mahdi¹

¹ Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University, Baghdad, Iraq

² Department of Pharmacy, Al-Rasheed University College, Baghdad, Iraq

³ College of Pharmacy, Al-Farahidi University, Baghdad, Iraq

Corresponding author: Hayder R. Fadhil (haider.raed@alrasheedcol.edu.iq)

Received 24 July 2024 ♦ Accepted 12 August 2024 ♦ Published 11 September 2024

Citation: Fadhil HR, Raauf AMR, Mahdi MF (2024) Synthesis, characterization, preliminary molecular docking, pharmacological activity, and ADME studies of some new pyrazoline derivatives as anti-breast cancer agents. *Pharmacia* 71: 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.71.e133015>

Abstract

This work studied the anti-breast cancer activities of pyrazoline-containing benzenesulfonamides (6–10) in vitro and silico. The GOLD suite performed molecular docking on the target human estrogen receptor and the PARP1 antagonist crystal structure, yielding comparable results using tamoxifen as a reference drug. Researchers tested these compounds (6–10) on two types of breast cancer cells (MCF-7 and MDA-MB-468) in the lab and found an antiproliferative activity that depended on the dose. Compounds 9 demonstrated a high docking score on PARP1 antagonist crystal structure in triple-negative breast cancer with a PLP fitness score of 93.24 and potential antiproliferative activity with an IC₅₀ of 2.79 μM on the MDA-MB-468 cell line. In contrast, compounds 8 and 10 showed promising activity on the MCF-7 cancer cell line with IC₅₀s of 7.4 and 17.96, respectively.

Keywords

pyrazole, triple-negative breast cancer, molecular docking, antiproliferative, ADME evaluation

Introduction

Cancer is universally acknowledged as one of the world's most serious health issues as well as a primary cause of mortality (Nepali et al. 2014). In the 21st century, successful cancer treatment remains a challenge. There is an urgent need for newer, safer anticancer drugs with an excellent range of cytotoxicity to tumor cells (Jin et al. 2012). Breast cancer (BC) is one of the most lethal diseases in the world (Din et al. 2022). Estrogen receptor (ER)

overexpression leads to the diagnosis of 80% of all new BC cases, classifying them as positive estrogen receptor (ER+) BC (Narzieyva and Jonibekov 2020; Tutzauer et al. 2020; Pham et al. 2021). The human estrogen receptor alpha (hER) is essential in physiology. BC ranks high among the world's most fatal diseases. The overexpression of ER categorizes most new BC cases, around 80%, as positive ER+ BC (Narzieyva and Jonibekov 2020; Tutzauer et al. 2020; Pham et al. 2021). Numerous physiological processes rely on the hER, including cell proliferation, survival,

and cancer metastasis (Dika et al. 2019; Jacenik et al. 2019; Maity 2019). Tamoxifen-neoplastic breast cancer (TNBC) is characterized by an overexpression of poly ADP ribose polymerase 1 (PARP1) and does not express the ER, progesterone receptor (PR), or human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2). Of all BC, 10%–15% are TNBC (Zagami and Carey 2022). The inability to overcome multi-drug resistance and having poor selectivity are the primary obstacles to treating tumors. Consequently, there has been an all-out effort to find new, highly selective compounds that can halt tumor growth, thereby eradicating malignancy and reducing the severity of BC. Heterocyclic scaffolds are present in both naturally occurring and artificially produced organic compounds of biological importance, and aromatic heterocycles are predominant in numerous medicinal compounds and motifs with physiological activity. Because they are involved in many important biological reactions, heterocyclic molecules are essential to all living systems (Morais et al. 2021). With two nitrogen atoms in its five-membered heterocyclic ring, pyrazoline is a vital member of the heterocyclic family (Kiyani et al. 2015). It possesses a variety of chemical, biological, and medicinal characteristics (Lv et al. 2010). A previous comprehensive study suggests that the pyrazoline ring system can synthesize and design new biologically active molecules with promising anticancer treatment potential (Tok et al. 2010). Fig. 1 illustrates the anticancer effects of several drugs that have pyrazoline scaffolds in their chemical structure (Amin et al. 2013; Rathore et al. 2014; Hamblin 2016; Maity 2019; Fadhil et al. 2022).

Because of their cytotoxicity, compounds generated from sulfonamides, such as pyrazole and pyrazoline, have attracted considerable attention from researchers (Rauf et al. 2022). Researchers are designing, docking molecularly, synthesizing, characterizing, and testing new pyrazoline derivatives with a sulfonamide moiety in vitro for efficacy.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and materials

All reagents and commonly used intermediates were obtained from commercial vendors (British company BDH and German company Sigma-Aldrich, hyper-chem, Hangxing RD., Hangzhou, China).

Characterization methods

The melting points were measured using the capillary method on an English-made Bamstead/Electrothermal 9100 instrument. The compounds as KBr disks were characterized using a Fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer (FTIR-6100 Type A). We conducted ¹H-NMR at 500 MHz with a Variant Agilent instrument. The varying ¹³C NMR quality was assessed using a 125 MHz Agilent.

Molecular structure synthesis

The following approaches were used to synthesize various novel pyrazoline derivatives, as shown in Scheme 1.

Synthesis of chalcone derivatives (1–5)

Intermediate compounds represented by different chalcone derivatives were synthesized via Claisen-Schmidt condensation of the respective 4-substituted benzaldehyde with 2-acetylpyridine, as described in the literature (Eid and George 2018).

Method A involves the production of molecules 2 and 4 that represent chalcone with nitro and chloro derivatives.

2-Acetylpyridine was slowly added over 2–3 hours to a solution containing 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide (10 mL), ethanol (5 mL), and the applicable aldehydes (4-nitrobenzaldehyde and 4-chlorobenzaldehyde) in the

Figure 1. Certain synthetic compounds containing pyrazoline motifs exhibit significant potential as anticancer agents.

Scheme 1. Represent the way to synthesize final compounds (6–10).

respective amounts of 17 mmol and 1.90 ml. The temperature was maintained at a steady 0 °C. After agitating the liquid for an additional 2 hours, we filtered it and rinsed it with abundant distilled water. Method A involves the production of molecules 2 and 4.

Method B involves the production of molecules 1, 3, and 5.

We introduced 17 mmol of 2-acetylpyridine and 17 mmol of the appropriate benzaldehydes (4-methoxybenzaldehyde, 4-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde, and benzaldehyde) into 100 mL of water when the temperature dropped below 5 °C. The mixture was vigorously agitated to achieve a highly dispersed emulsion, and then a 10 mL solution of 10% sodium hydroxide was added. The mixture was subjected to two rounds of mixing and then undisturbed overnight at a temperature of 4 °C. It is essential to avoid agitating the solution, as this might lead to phase separation and lower yields. The compound underwent phase separation upon agitation, transforming into an oily state that solidified. Perform filtration and wash with an abundant amount of distilled water.

The following is a general method for synthesizing pyrazoline derivatives (6–10)

Equal quantities of compounds (1–10) (2 mmol) and 4-hydrazine benzenesulfonamide hydrochloride (2 mmol, 0.8947 g) were combined in 5 ml of absolute ethanol. Potassium hydroxide (5 mmol, 0.28 g) was then added. The mixture was heated and refluxed for 8 hours. After

cooling, the precipitate was separated, filtered, and washed with abundant distilled water (Daina et al. 2017).

The compound (1) is (E)-3-(4-methoxyphenyl)-1-(pyridine-2-yl) prop-2-en-1-one

The substance is a green powder with a 79–80 °C melting point. The substance has a yield of 87%. The infrared spectrum shows peaks at 3057.27 cm⁻¹ (C-H of aromatic), 2974.33 and 2841.24 cm⁻¹ (O-CH₃), 1666.55 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1599.04.18 cm⁻¹ (C=C of alkene), 1570.1 and 1520.3 cm⁻¹ (C=C and C=N of aromatic), and 1259.56 cm⁻¹ (C-O-CH₃). The proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum (500 MHz, DMSO, δ) shows peaks at 3.80 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.00–7.02 (1H, d, CH of a vinyl proton), 7.65–7.14 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.00–8.03 (1H, d, CH of β vinyl proton), and 8.07–8.78 (3H, m, Ar-H). The carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum (DMSO-d₆, ppm, 125 MHz) shows peaks at 55.83 (O-CH₃), 115.30–162.00 (11 C of aromatic ring), 122.83 (C=C next to C=O), 144.5 (C=C next to aromatic ring), and 188.95 (C=O).

The compound (2) is (E)-3-(4-nitrophenyl)-1-(pyridin-2-yl) prop-2-en-1-one

The substance is a light brown powder with a melting point of 153–154 °C. The substance has a yield of 77%. For example, at 3057.27 cm⁻¹, the absorption peaks are for C-H of aromatics, 1666.55 cm⁻¹ for C=O, 1604.83 cm⁻¹ for C=C of alkenes, 1589.40 and 1514.17 cm⁻¹ for C=C and C=N of aromatics, and 1344.43 cm⁻¹ for NO₂. The proton

nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum (500 MHz, DMSO, ϵ) has peaked at 7.72 (1H, d, CH of α vinyl proton), 7.88–8.04 (3H, m, Ar-H), 8.05–8.06 (1H, d, CH of β vinyl proton), and 8.07–8.80 (5H, m, Ar-H). The carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum (DMSO-d₆, ppm, 125 MHz) has peaks at 123.09–153.46 (11 C of the aromatic ring), 130.19 (C=C next to C=O), 141.39 (C=C next to the aromatic ring), and 189.01 (C=O).

The compound (3) is (E)-3-(4-(dimethylamino) phenyl)-1-(pyridin-2-yl) prop-2-en-1-one

The substance is a light orange powder with a melting point of 82–83 °C. The yield is 85%. The infrared spectrum has absorption peaks at 3041.84 cm⁻¹ (C-H of aromatic), 2910.68 and 2804.59 cm⁻¹ (CH₃), 1668.48 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1599.04 cm⁻¹ (C=C of alkene), 1539.25 and 1437.02 cm⁻¹ (C=C and C=N of aromatic), and 1165.04 cm⁻¹ (N-CH₃). The proton nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum (500 MHz, DMSO, ϵ) has signals at 3.00 (6H, s, N[CH₃]₂), 6.73–6.66 (1H, d, CH of α vinyl proton), 7.62–7.64 (4H, m, Ar-H), 7.66–7.68 (1H, d, CH of β vinyl proton), and 7.77–8.76 (4H, m, Ar-H). The carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance spectrum (DMSO-d₆, ppm, 125 MHz) has signals at 40.12 (N-CH₃), 111.51–154.65 (11 C of aromatic ring), 122.64 (C=C next to C=O), 149.46 (C=C next to aromatic ring), and 190.29 (C=O).

The compound (4) is (E)-3-(4-chlorophenyl)-1-(pyridin-2-yl) prop-2-en-1-one

The substance is a light green powder with a 94–96 °C melting point. The compound has a 79% yield. The infrared (IR) spectrum shows absorption peaks at 3057.27 cm⁻¹ (C-H of aromatic), 1674.27 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1606.76 cm⁻¹ (C=C of alkene), 1585.54 and 1492.95 cm⁻¹ (C=C and C=N of aromatic), and 1089.92 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). The proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) spectrum, recorded at 500 MHz in DMSO, shows peaks at 7.35–7.38 (2H, m, Ar-H), 7.46–7.48 (1H, d, CH of α vinyl proton), 7.66–8.07 (5H, m, Ar-H), 8.22–8.25 (1H, d, CH of β vinyl proton), and 8.77–8.78 (1H, m, Ar-H). The carbon-13 nuclear magnetic resonance (¹³C NMR) spectrum, recorded at 125 MHz in DMSO-d₆, shows peaks at 122.96–153.75 (11 C of the aromatic ring), 128.46 (C=C next to C=O), 142.95 (C=C next to the aromatic ring), and 189.05 (C=O).

The compound (5) is (E)-3-phenyl-1-(pyridine-2-yl) prop-2-en-1-one

The substance is a pale green powder with a 60–61 °C melting point. The yield is 71%. The infrared spectrum shows absorption peaks at 3063.06 cm⁻¹ (C-H of aromatic), 1668.48 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1604.83 cm⁻¹ (C=C of alkene), and 1585.54 and 1489.1 cm⁻¹ (C=C and C=N of aromatic). The ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, DMSO, ϵ) shows signals at 7.22–7.86 (6H, m, Ar-H), 7.88–7.89 (1H, d, CH of α vinyl proton), 8.0–8.14 (2H, m, Ar-H), 8.2–8.30 (1H, d, CH of β vinyl proton), and 8.82–8.83 (1H, m, Ar-H). The

¹³C NMR spectrum (DMSO-d₆, ppm, 125 MHz) shows signals at 123.47–156.06 (11 C of the aromatic ring), 130.32 (C=C next to C=O), 146.71 (C=C next to the aromatic ring), and 191.36 (C=O).

The compound (6) is 4-(5-(4-methoxyphenyl)-3-(pyridin-2-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl) benzenesulfonamide

The substance is a dark green crystal with a melting point of 139–141 °C. The yield of the compound is 87%. The infrared spectrum shows absorption peaks at 3371.68 and 3271.38 cm⁻¹, indicating the presence of NH₂ groups. A peak at 3057.27 cm⁻¹ suggests the presence of aromatic C-H bonds. Peaks at 2966.63 and 2841.24 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of CH₃ groups. Lastly, a peak at 1597.11 cm⁻¹ indicates the presence of a C=N bond in the pyrazoline ring. The infrared spectrum shows absorption peaks at 1508.38 and 1465.95 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the C=C and C=N bonds of the aromatic compound. Additionally, peaks at 1346.7 cm⁻¹ and 1153.9 cm⁻¹ indicate the presence of a SO₂N group. The ¹H NMR spectrum, recorded at 500 MHz in DMSO, reveals the following chemical shifts: 3.17 ppm (1H, doublet of doublets, CH₂ pyrazoline), 3.79 ppm (3H, singlet, O-CH₃), 3.94 ppm (1H, doublet of doublets, CH₂ pyrazoline), 5.62 ppm (1H, doublet of doublets, CH of pyrazoline), 6.89 ppm (2H, doublet, H of aromatic ortho to OCH₃), 7.06 ppm (2H, singlet, SO₂NH₂), and 7.13–8.86 ppm (12H, multiplet, Ar-H). The ¹³C NMR spectrum, recorded in DMSO-d₆ at 125 MHz, shows the following chemical shifts: 43.34 ppm (C-5, pyrazoline), 55.50 ppm (O-CH₃), 62.60 ppm (C-4, pyrazoline), 112.89–151.34 ppm (16 carbons of the aromatic ring), 146.03 ppm (C=N of diazole), and 159.07 ppm (aromatic carbon linked to O-CH₃).

The compound (7) is 4-(5-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-(pyridin-2-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl) benzenesulfonamide

The substance is a dark brown crystal with a melting point of 192–194 °C. The compound has a 72% yield. At 3362.04 cm⁻¹ and 3252.09 cm⁻¹, the NH₂ group absorbs the most light, followed by the aromatic C-H group at 3063.06 cm⁻¹, the C=N group at 1595.18 cm⁻¹, and the C=C and C=N groups of the aromatic ring at 1518.03 cm⁻¹ and 1398.51 cm⁻¹. Additionally, there are absorption peaks at 1344.43 cm⁻¹ and 1157.33 cm⁻¹ for the SO₂N group. The ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz) The 500 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum (ϵ) has peaks at 3.05 (1H, dd, CH₂ pyrazoline), 3.98 (1H, dd, CH₂ pyrazoline), 5.44 (1H, dd, CH of pyrazoline), 6.96 (2H, s, SO₂NH₂), and 7.06–8.69 (12 H, m, Ar-H). The ¹³C NMR spectrum was recorded at a frequency of 125 M. We observed the following chemical shifts: 41.43 ppm (N [CH₃]₂), 46.22 ppm (C-5, pyrazoline), 63.31 ppm (C-4, pyrazoline), and a range of 108.21 to 144.11 ppm (17 carbons of the aromatic ring). Additionally, we observed a peak at 148.21 ppm, which corresponds to the C=N bond of the diazole.

4-(5-(4-(dimethylamino) phenyl)-3-(pyridin-2-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl) benzenesulfonamide (8)

The substance is a dark brown crystal with a melting point of 192–194 °C. The compound has a 72% yield. The NH₂ group absorbs the most light at 3362.04 cm⁻¹ and 3252.09 cm⁻¹, the aromatic C-H bond at 3063.06 cm⁻¹, the C=N bond at 1595.18 cm⁻¹, and the C=C and C=N bonds in the aromatic ring at 1518.03 cm⁻¹ and 1398.51 cm⁻¹. Additionally, there are absorption peaks at 1344.43 cm⁻¹ and 1157.33 cm⁻¹ for the SO₂N group. The ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, DMSO, ε) shows peaks at 3.05 (1H, dd) and 3.98 (1H, dd) for the CH₂ groups in the pyrazoline ring, 5.44 (1H, dd) for the CH group in the pyrazoline ring, 6.96 (2H, s) for the SO₂NH₂ group, and a range of peaks from 7.06 to 8.69 (12H, m) for the aromatic protons. The ¹³C NMR spectrum (measured at 125 MHz) of the compound in DMSO-d₆ shows the following chemical shifts in parts per million (ppm): 41.43 for the N[CH₃]₂ group, 46.22 for the C-5 atom in the pyrazoline moiety, 63.31 for the C-4 atom, and 108.21 to 144.11 for the 17 carbon atoms in the aromatic ring. Additionally, a peak at 148.21 ppm corresponds to the C=N bond in the diazole group.

The compound (9) is 4-(5-(4-chlorophenyl)-3-(pyridin-2-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl) benzenesulfonamide

We obtained a pale brown crystal with a melting point of 119–121 °C and a yield of 77%. The infrared spectrum has absorption peaks at 3365.9 and 3292.60 cm⁻¹ for the NH₂ group, 3092.82 cm⁻¹ for aromatic C-H bonds, 1595.48 cm⁻¹ for the C=N bond, and 1494.88 and 1404.21 cm⁻¹ for the C=C and C=N bonds in the aromatic ring. We observe additional peaks at 1327.07 and 1149.61 cm⁻¹ for the SO₂N group and 1089.23 cm⁻¹ for the C-Cl bond. The proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H NMR) spectrum, recorded at 500 MHz in DMSO, shows peaks at 3.23 and 3.98 ppm for the CH₂ groups in the pyrazoline moiety and 5.77 ppm for the CH group in the pyrazoline ring. The two protons of the SO₂NH₂ group exhibit a singlet peak at 7.09 ppm. The aromatic protons appear as multiples in the 7.1–8.69 ppm range, totaling 12 protons. ¹³C NMR shows peaks at 42.81 ppm for C-5 in the pyrazoline ring, 62.70 ppm for C-4 in the pyrazoline ring, and a range of peaks from 111.74 to 149.52 ppm for the 17 carbon atoms in the aromatic ring. The spectrum was recorded at 125 MHz in DMSO-d₆. Additionally, the C=N bond in the pyrazoline ring exhibits a peak at 140.58 ppm.

The compound (10) is 4-(5-phenyl-3-(pyridin-2-yl)-4,5-dihydro-1H-pyrazol-1-yl) benzenesulfonamide

The brown crystal has a melting point of 96–98 °C and a yield of 62%. The infrared spectrum has absorption peaks at 3340.82 and 3288.74 cm⁻¹ for the NH₂ group, 3061.13 cm⁻¹ for aromatic C-H bonds, 1591.33 cm⁻¹ for C=N bonds, and 1502.60 and 1464.02 cm⁻¹ for C=C and C=N bonds in the aromatic ring. Additionally, there are

absorption peaks at 1332.68 cm⁻¹ and 1153.47 cm⁻¹ for the SO₂N group. The ¹H NMR spectrum (500 MHz, DMSO) shows peaks at 3.22 and 3.99 ppm for CH₂ groups in the pyrazoline moiety, 5.73 ppm for a CH group in the pyrazoline moiety, 7.07 ppm for two protons in the SO₂NH₂ group, and a range of peaks from 7.16 to 8.62 ppm for 12 aromatic protons. The ¹³C NMR spectrum (DMSO-d₆, 125 MHz) shows peaks at 43.02 ppm for C-5 in the pyrazoline moiety, 63.35 ppm for C-4 in the pyrazoline moiety, and 17 carbon atoms in the aromatic ring with a range of peaks from 111.62 to 148.23 ppm. There is also a peak at 139.38 ppm for the C=N bond in the pyrazoline moiety.

Methods of computation

Fig. 2 illustrates the computational preparation of this study. We docked our compounds using the CCDC GOLD Suite (v. 5.6.2). The CCDC Hermes visualizer (1.9.2) shows ligands, receptors, hydrogen bonding, short contacts, and bond length calculations. We used ChemBioOffice (v. 17.1) to draw the structures of our ligands and reference medicine compounds. The synthetic drug ADME was determined using the Swiss ADME server (Daina et al. 2017).

Figure 2. Computational protocol for the desired compounds.

ADME procedures

The compounds (6–10) were formed using ChembioOffice software and subsequently transformed into SMILE names using the Swiss ADME tool. The Swiss ADME program also predicted the compounds' pharmacokinetic and physicochemical parameters. We evaluated the small molecule's lipophilicity and polarity using a boiled egg (Odoemelam et al. 2022).

Ligands and receptor preparation

The protein data bank (PDB) gave us the crystal structures of the human estrogen receptor and the PARP1 antagonist, and SwissPDB Viewer (SPDBV) version 3.7 was used to add

any missing atoms. To create a protein's crystal structure, we remove water molecules that do not influence binding and retain those that do. Next, hydrogen was added to the amino acid residues to bring them into the correct ionized and tautomeric state. We minimized the energy of the generated molecules using CheBio3D (v. 19.1) and the MM2 force field.

Molecular docking protocol

We performed the molecular docking using the licensed version of genetic optimization for ligand docking (GOLD) (v. 2020.3.0). The Hermes visualizer application within GOLD successfully executed the docking operation. Nucleotides and protein residues within 10 Angstroms of reference ligands found in protein structure complexes make up the docking binding site. The proteins were obtained from the PDB website, specifically from PDB entries 1ERR and 5HA9. The active site radius was determined to be 10 Angstroms (Å) using the protein reference ligand. Then, the chemscore kinase was used as a configuration template. We executed the scoring function using ChemPLP. The GOLD docking technique utilized default values for all parameters, and the solutions were evaluated based on the fitness function of piecewise linear potential (CHEMPLP). The docking findings, including the docked posture, binding mode, and binding free energy, were used to assess the ligands' interactions with the protein residues in the active site of the human estrogen receptor.

Antiproliferative ASSAY

We investigated the anticancer effect of (6–10) on the viability of breast cancer cell lines (MCF-7 and MDA) using the MTT test methodology. The College of Pharmacy at Mustansiriyah University conducted this investigation.

Determining the value of the half-maximum inhibitory concentration (IC50)

Based on the in vitro MTT experiment, the IC50 value indicates the concentration of the tested chemicals (ranging from 6 to 10) needed to decrease cell viability by 50%. Based on the findings of the in vitro MTT assay, the IC50 values were calculated for 6 to 10 compounds 72 hours after the cells were exposed to these compounds.

Quantitative analysis of data using statistical methods

Graph pad Prism and nonlinear curve fitting software were used to do statistical analyses of the IC50 and MTT

test data for the medicines we looked at (6–10) on MCF-7 and MDA-MB-468 cells. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted using the Tukey test to compare all groups within the same MTT plate (using both prism and software). P values exceeding 0.05 determined the statistical significance.

Results and discussion

Analysis of the ADME findings

The drug-like characteristics of all the final compounds (610) were calculated using Lipinski's rule of five (Kadela-Tomanek et al. 2021). The current study routinely uses this procedure, known as Pfizer's rule of five (RO5), to screen compounds for drug design leads. The qualities of oral pharmaceuticals that Lipinski's rule of five requires include molecular weight 500, log p 5, hydrogen bond acceptor 10, and hydrogen bond donor 5. Also, the compounds' topological polar surface area (TPSA) and influencing bioavailability were calculated. As a result, passively absorbed drugs with TPSAs > 140 Å have low bioavailability. According to ADME prediction data, all compounds except (7) had TPSA below 140 Å, reaching 106.26, 142.85, 100.27, 97.03, and 97.03 Å. All chemicals enter systemic circulation because of their 0.55 bioavailability. Table 1 shows Lipinski's rule of five (RO5). All derivatives met the key topological descriptors and fingerprints of the molecular drug-likeness structure, such as LogP and LogS.

All chemicals, except (7), had high GI absorption scores, which measure xenobiotic absorption from the gastrointestinal tract following oral administration. It has been expected that the present compounds have high absorption of intestinal solids, while compound 7 showed limited absorption.

Analysis of docking final results

The last compounds (6–10) were successfully docked using the GOLD Suite software. Ligands undergo energy minimization to correct distorted geometries by repositioning atoms to alleviate internal constraints. Energy reduction restores the geometry and leads to a minimum energy state. The complex's fitness function ability has been observed for all requested molecules. We rated the compounds (6–10) and tamoxifen's binding affinity to the human estrogen receptor with PDB (1ERR), as well as the compounds (6–10) and a new PARP1 an-

Table 1. The ADME result for the final derivatives.

Comp.	H-bond acceptor	H-bond donor	MR	TPSA (Å ²)	GI Abs	BBB permeant	Bioavailability	Lipinski violation
6	6	1	117.54	106.26	High	NO	0.55	0 violation
7	7	1	119.87	142.85	Low	NO	0.55	0 violation
8	5	1	125.26	100.27	High	NO	0.55	0 violation
9	5	1	116.06	97.03	High	NO	0.55	0 violation
10	5	1	111.05	97.03	High	NO	0.55	0 violation

Figure 10. IC₅₀ dose response curves for compound (8) on MCF-7.

Figure 11. IC₅₀ dose response curves for compound 10 on the MCF-7 cell line for compound 10, respectively.

References

- Amin KM, Eissa AA, Abou-Seri SM, Awadallah FM, Hassan GS (2013) Synthesis and biological evaluation of novel coumarin–pyrazoline hybrids endowed with phenylsulfonyl moiety as antitumor agents. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 60: 187–198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2012.12.004>
- Daina A, Michielin O, Zoete V (2017) SwissADME: a free web tool to evaluate pharmacokinetics, drug-likeness and medicinal chemistry friendliness of small molecules. *Scientific Reports* 7(1): 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep42717>
- Dika E, Patrizi A, Lambertini M, Manuelpillai N, Fiorentino M, Altamari A, Scarfi F (2019) Estrogen receptors and melanoma: a review. *Cells* 8(11): 1463. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells8111463>
- Din NMU, Dar RA, Rasool M, Assad A (2022) Breast cancer detection using deep learning: Datasets, methods, and challenges ahead. *Computers in Biology and Medicine* 149: 106073. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compbiomed.2022.106073>
- Eid NM, George RF (2018) Facile synthesis of some pyrazoline-based compounds with promising anti-inflammatory activity. *Future Medicinal Chemistry* 10(2): 183–199. <https://doi.org/10.4155/fmc-2017-0144>
- Fadhil HR, Mahdi MF, Raauf AMR (2022) Molecular docking, synthesis, characterization and antiproliferative antiproliferative evaluation of pyrazoline derivatives. *Biochemical and Cellular Archives* 22: 2927–2936.
- Hamblin MR (2016) Shining light on the head: photobiomodulation for brain disorders. *BBA Clinical* 6: 113–124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbacli.2016.09.002>
- Jacenic D, Beswick EJ, Krajewska WM, Prossnitz ER (2019) G protein-coupled estrogen receptor in colon function, immune regulation and carcinogenesis. *World Journal of Gastroenterology* 25(30): 4092. <https://doi.org/10.3748/wjg.v25.i30.4092>
- Jin C, Liang YJ, He H, Fu L (2011) Synthesis and antitumor activity of ureas containing pyrimidinyl group. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 46(1): 429–432. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2010.11.026>
- Kadela-Tomanek M, Jastrzębska M, Chrobak E, Bębenek E, Boryczka S (2021) Chromatographic and computational screening of lipophilicity and pharmacokinetics of newly synthesized betulin-1, 4-quinone hybrids. *Processes* 9(2): 376. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr9020376>
- Kiyani H, Albooyeh F, Fallahnezhad S (2015) Synthesis of new pyrazolyl-1, 3-diazabicyclo [3.1.0] hexe-3-ene derivatives. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1091: 163–169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2015.02.069>
- Lv PC, Sun J, Luo Y, Yang Y, Zhu HL (2010) Design, synthesis, and structure-activity relationships of pyrazole derivatives as potential FabH inhibitors. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters* 20(15): 4657–4660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2010.05.105>

Conclusion

The evaluation of the products shows that pyrazolines containing sulphonamide groups have outstanding anti-breast cancer action. The docking tests demonstrated a high binding affinity with both the human estrogen receptor and PARP1 antagonist in compounds (6–10), as confirmed by in vivo investigations. Compound 9 has potent action on the MDA-MB0-648 cell line, but compounds 8 and 10 have more significant activity on the MCF-7 cell line. In addition, the ADME study demonstrated that all produced compounds met the Lipinski criterion except for compound (7).

Author contributions

Hayder R. Fadhil contributed to the idea, data curation, investigation, methodology, software development, and project supervision. Monther F. Mahdi specializes in document validation, writing, review, and editing. Ayad M.R. Raauf contributed to the project by providing visualization, writing the original text, and reviewing and correcting the content.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank the chairman and colleagues of the Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry at the College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University, for their assistance and support. There is no funding.

- Maity K (2019) Synthesis, characterization, molecular docking and evaluation of the anticancer activity of 2-pyrazoline derivatives. *Asian Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmacology* 5(5): 1010–1021. <https://doi.org/10.31024/ajpp.2019.5.5.22>
- Morais CS, Mengarda AC, Miguel FB, Enes KB, Rodrigues VC, Espirito-Santo MCC, de Moraes J (2021) Pyrazoline derivatives as promising novel antischistosomal agents. *Scientific Reports* 11(1): 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-02792-0>
- Narzeyva DF, Jonibekov JJ (2020) Morphological features of tumor in different treatment options for patients with locally advanced breast cancer. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin* 7: 105–107. <https://doi.org/10.47494/mesb.2020.1.151>
- Nepali K, Sharma S, Sharma M, Bedi PM, Dhar KL (2014) Rational approaches, design strategies, structure-activity relationship, and mechanistic insights for anticancer hybrids. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry* 22(77): 422–487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ej-mech.2014.03.018>
- Odoemelam CS, Hunter E, Simms J, Ahmad Z, Chang MW, Percival B, Wilson PB (2022) In silico ligand docking approaches to characterise the binding of known allosteric modulators to the glucagon-like peptide 1 receptor and prediction of ADME/Tox properties. *Applied Biosciences* 1(2): 143–162. <https://doi.org/10.3390/applbiosci1020010>
- Pham TH, Page YL, Percevault F, Ferriere F, Flouriot G, Pakdel F (2021) Apigenin, a partial antagonist of the estrogen receptor (ER), inhibits ER-positive breast cancer cell proliferation through Akt/FOXM1 signaling. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 22(1): 470. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22010470>
- Raaf AM, Omar TN, Mahdi MF, Fadhil HR (2022) Synthesis, molecular docking and anti-inflammatory evaluation of new trisubstituted pyrazoline derivatives bearing benzenesulfonamide moiety. *Natural Product Research* 38(2): 253–260. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786419.2022.2117174>
- Rathore P, Yaseen S, Ovais S, Bashir R, Yaseen R, Hameed AD, Javed K (2014) Synthesis and evaluation of some new pyrazoline substituted benzene sulfonylureas as potential antiproliferative antiproliferative agents. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters* 24(7): 1685–1691. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2014.02.059>
- Tok F, Abas Bİ, Çevik Ö, Koçyiğit-Kaymakçioğlu B (2020) Design, synthesis and biological evaluation of some new 2-Pyrazoline derivatives as potential anticancer agents. *Bioorganic Chemistry* 102: 104063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bioorg.2020.104063>
- Tutzauer J, Sjöström M, Bendahl PO, Rydén L, Fernö M, Leeb-Lundberg LF, Alkner S (2020) Plasma membrane expression of G protein-coupled estrogen receptor (GPER)/G protein-coupled receptor 30 (GPR30) is associated with worse outcome in metachronous contralateral breast cancer. *PLOS ONE* 15(4): e0231786. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0231786>
- Zagami P, Carey LA (2022) Triple-negative breast cancer: Pitfalls and progress. *NPJ Breast Cancer* 8(1): 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41523-022-00468-0>